

	Arbor Corticosterone						
72a Methanol	0.28	72a Methanol					
CJM006 Corticosterone	0.14	0.34	CJM006 Corticosterone				
72a Diethylether	0.11	0.87	0.13	72a Diethylether			
69a Methanol	0.11	0.48	0.33	0.4	69a Methanol		
69a Diethylether	0.09	0.43	0.3	0.43	0.96	69a Diethylether	
72T Methanol	-0.02	0.38	0.21	0.45	0.83	0.86	72T Methanol
72T Diethylether	-0.12	0.29	0.12	0.42	0.79	0.84	0.94